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Template: Datasheet for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets

Version 2 – July 2025

This template is the second version of the template to describe Cultural Heritage datasets that was introduced in Alkemade et al. 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>). The main structure of the first version followed Gebru's (2021) and Pushkarna's templates (2022); the second version introduces some more differences, especially as an attempt to align better with the DCAT Application Profile for data portals which is getting traction in Europe (DCAT-AP).¹ The superscripts added to section headings refer to items in the bibliography at the very end, which have inspired the section by providing explanations and/or discussions about its topic.

Notes on filling the template. This template is structured in three levels, the top-level providing fields for a high-level description of a dataset along a specific dimension, and the lower levels allowing a datasheet creator to indicate more specific details, possibly using more controlled expressions. Cultural heritage datasets are heterogeneous, therefore not every item of the template fits; users of the template should decide on what is helpful and what can be discarded. Not all parts of the template will be uniformly relevant to all datasets or equally applicable to features within a single dataset. However, to achieve compatibility with DCAT-AP, it is recommended to fill the fields that correspond to DCAT-AP elements, especially those marked as DCAT-AP-mandatory^{DCAT-AP:M}. For the sake of completeness, if you are certain that a field does not apply to the dataset at hand (as opposed to a situation where you simply do not have the information) please fill this field with "Not applicable".

Title^{DCAT-AP:M}

[Provide a title for the dataset.]

Description^{c,b,f}

[Provide a brief descriptive overview of the dataset ('at a glance').^{DCAT-AP:M} Briefly summarise the dataset, its intended use and the supported tasks. Give an overview of the contents of the dataset (data and metadata, only data or metadata; relating to physical, digitised or born-digital objects, etc.) how and why the dataset was created. The summary should describe the domain, topic, genre covered, keywords, and other relevant metadata. Clearly articulate the reasons for creating the dataset and promote transparency about funding interests. For what purpose was the dataset created? Was there a specific task in mind? Was there a specific gap that needed to be filled? Who created the dataset (e.g., which team, research group) and on behalf of which entity (e.g., company, institution, organisation)? Who funded the creation of the dataset?]

Homepage

[Add the URL of the homepage of the dataset here if available.]

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>

Publisher

[Either the individual publisher or the responsible organisation should be provided - preferably the latter. Note that this is likely to be different from “Dataset Curators” and “Other Contributors” to be filled in other sections.]

Dataset Curators^c

[List the key people involved in collecting the dataset and their affiliation(s). Dataset curators are encouraged to insert some information about their positionality here, e.g. in the form of a short bio containing information on their formation, role and function within the CHI or project and the task(s) with which they were entrusted during the creation of the dataset.]

Other Contributors^c

[Credit the additional people who have contributed to this dataset other than those who have curated and published it and annotators (as per the section below).]

Point of Contact

[If known, name, email and/or ORCID of at least one person or organisational contact the reader can reach for questions and comments about the dataset and/or the datasheet. This is especially relevant as datasets can change, and datasheets should be conceived of as flexible and dynamic objects which change according to the version of a dataset documented by them. Therefore, please indicate a reliable contact in order to enable the incorporation of responses and comments into a new version.]

Papers and/or Other References

[If the dataset was introduced by a paper or there was a paper written describing the dataset, add URL here.]

Supported Tasks and Shared Tasks^c

[Give a brief description of the task(s) identified for this dataset, metrics, and suggested models. For each task, also provide reference to any shared task the dataset is part of.]

AI Category

[The category(ies) of the AI application(s) that the dataset is suitable for. This field is free text but it is advised to refer to shared vocabularies like the AI4Culture² one (“Automation”, “Copywriting”, “Generative Art”, “Image editing”...) or the HuggingFace taxonomy of tasks.³]

Type of Cultural Heritage Application

[The type(s) of cultural heritage application(s) that the resource is applied in or could be relevant for. This field is free text, but it is advised to refer to shared

² <https://ai4culture.eu/>

³ <https://huggingface.co/tasks>

vocabularies like TADIRAH⁴ or the AI4Culture categories (Collection management, Collection search, Metadata enrichment).]

(Cultural Heritage) Application Example

[Specific instance(s) of application (link to a project page, paper or other).]

Distribution^b

[Dataset creators should provide answers to the following points: distribution information, dissemination strategy, licences, DOIs, third party involvement and restrictions.]

Data Access URL DCAT-AP:M

[Indicate the URL where the dataset can be accessed, possibly on an online repository, e.g., if the dataset is hosted on GitHub.]

Licensing Information^c

[Provide the licence(s) for the current data distribution and link to the licence(s) webpage(s) if available. Be aware that some cases may exhibit different licenses for (parts of) metadata and content. Identifying different levels of copyright and constraints may also be needed – for example these related to the original material and these related to a performance of it.]

File Format

[Describe the format(s) and encoding in which the data is available, using a MIME type when available: text/csv, UTF-8, image/jpeg, audio/flac, video/mpeg...]

Citation Information^c

[Provide a well formatted reference for the dataset, preferably using BibTeX. If the dataset has a DOI or other kind of persistent identifier, please provide it here.]

Composition^{b,e}

[Provide dataset consumers with the information about the contents of the dataset, which are expected to be relevant for their chosen tasks: the kind of objects in the dataset, the structure and organisation of the dataset, the language in which it is provided and some elementary statistics.]

Dataset Category

[Select the appropriate answer: content and/or metadata.]

Media Category

[Describe the category(ies) of media (modality) associated with the dataset. For example using the list in the Europeana Data Model, an OCR dataset (including full-

⁴ <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/>

text and images of documents) is associated with 'image' and 'text', a sound archive is associated with 'audio', 3D models of historical monuments are associated with '3D model', a dataset that contains only descriptive metadata is associated with 'text'.]

Object Type

[Indicate one or more specialised type(s) of CH objects covered by the dataset, like 'newspaper', 'painting', 'sound recording', 'historical monuments', 'web pages'. NB: using keywords or concepts from a relevant standard vocabulary like AAT⁵ or RDA Content Type⁶ here will help make the dataset better findable.]

Dataset Structure^c

[Provide a systematic description of the (conceptual and/or technical) dataset, including schemas and hierarchical organisation.]

Data Instances^c

[Provide an example (possibly a data snippet) and brief description of a typical instance in the dataset. What metadata are available for the dataset items? Alternatively, it is possible to include the URL of an image, audio content or 3D model (possibly a snapshot of it).]

Data Fields^{c,f}

[List and describe the fields present in the dataset. Mention their data type (number, string, date, coordinates...), and whether they are used as input or output in any of the tasks the dataset currently supports. If the data has e.g. span indices, describe their attributes, such as whether they are at the character or word level, whether they are contiguous or not, etc. Similarly, if the dataset contains IDs, state whether their structure has an inherent meaning, and whether they should be interpreted as a mapping to other datasets or pointing to relationships between data points.

NB: if the list conforms to an existing standard or best practice, it is recommended to use the "compliance with standard" field below.]

Compliance with Standard(s)

[A standard data model or schema and/or established data practice, for example W3C Web Annotation, that the dataset conforms to. It is appropriate to use a web identifier or link to the standard or its documentation, like <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>. It can be version-specific, like <http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/bibframe-2-5-0/>.

NB: these standards or practices could be domain-specific.]

Data Splits^c

[Describe and name machine learning splits in the dataset if there are any. Describe any criteria for splitting the data, if used. If there are differences

⁵ <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>

⁶ <https://www.rdaregistry.info/termList/RDAContentType/>

between the splits (e.g. if the training annotations are machine-generated and the development and test ones are created by humans, or if different numbers of annotators contributed to each example), describe them here. Provide the sizes of each split. If appropriate, provide any descriptive statistics for the features, such as average length. Are there recommended data splits (e.g., training, development/validation, testing)? If so, please provide a description of these splits, explaining the rationale behind them.]

Language^c

[Explicitly mention the languages present in the dataset (possibly in broad terms, e.g. translations between several pairs of European languages). Describe relevant details about specifics of the language using e.g. BCP-47 codes.⁷]

Descriptive Statistics

[The information presented in this section should be chosen on the basis of whether it tells something valuable and about the richness of the dataset. Be reminded that it depends on the intended purpose of a dataset whether the numbers and metrics provided can be of use. How large is the dataset, both in cardinality and in disk storage?^e What are its key descriptive statistics per field? Note that the statistics that reflect the richness of data are likely to be domain-specific, i.e. for musical datasets, you might use average recording length, distribution by genre, sampling rate, number of tracks, etc.

Consider which statistics should be put into the bias section below to avoid overlap. For example, if some objects in a dataset don't have metadata about their creators, this can be flagged in the general statistics as a quality issue that possibly hinders application development. If there is a gender imbalance in the available creators this could be indicated in the section about biases.]

Data Collection Process^{b,e,f}

[Elicit information that may help researchers and practitioners to re-use this dataset or create alternative datasets with similar characteristics.]

Curation Rationale^{c,e,f}

[What need motivated the creation of this dataset? What were some of the reasons underlying the major choices involved in putting it together?]

Source Data^{c,f}

[This section describes the source data (e.g. news text and headlines, translated sentences,...).]

Initial Data Collection^c

[Describe the data collection process. Describe any criteria for data selection, filtering or harvesting (in particular, list any keywords or search terms used). If

⁷ <https://tools.ietf.org/html/bcp47>

possible and relevant, include runtime information for the collection process. If data was collected from other pre-existing datasets, link to the source here.]

Source Data Producers^c

[State whether the source data or source objects were produced by humans (such as the writers of books) or machine generated and provide a description for them. If available, include self-reported demographic or identity information for the creators of the source data or objects, but avoid inferring this information. Instead, state that this information is unknown. See Larson, 2017^d for using identity categories as variables, particularly gender.]

Digitisation Pipeline^e

[Indicate information (paradata) on the digitization process, which can be relevant for reuse; for example, the motivation for digitisation (e.g. conservation, research project, or else) and/or technical metadata such as the image capture equipment and software/parameters used for any OCR/HTR processing and/or the level of quality of the results. If applicable, describe in what way digitisation presents another layer of selection of the whole of a collection available in a cultural heritage institution; provide selection criteria and metrics that show how it has influenced the transformation of this collection into the current dataset (e.g. what part has been digitised and what not).^e State if there was no such selection.]

Preprocessing and Cleaning^{b,f}

[Provide dataset consumers with the information they need to determine whether the “raw” data has been processed in ways that are compatible with their chosen tasks (for example using anonymisation). If the data was modified or normalised after being collected (e.g. if the data is word-tokenized), describe the process and the tools used.]

Annotations^{c,f}

[If the dataset contains annotations which are not part of the initial data collection, describe them in the following paragraphs. If annotations are published as a separate dataset (with its own datasheet being the one filled here) then please reflect the information below in the fields above, especially “Initial Data Collection” and “Source Data Producers?”.]

Annotation Process^c

[If applicable, describe the annotation process and any tools used, or state otherwise. Describe the amount of data annotated, if not all. Have the annotations been aggregated? What are the limitations of the annotation method? Describe or reference annotation guidelines provided to the annotators. If available, provide inter-annotator statistics. Describe any annotation validation processes.]

Annotators^{c,f}

[If annotations were collected for the source data (such as class labels or syntactic parsers), state whether the annotations were produced by humans

or machine generated. Describe the people or systems who originally created the annotations and their selection criteria, if applicable. Is socio-demographic information on the annotators available? Can the annotators be assigned to a specific population group? Is the socio-demographic data on the annotators available to the users of the dataset? If available, include self-reported demographic or identity information for the annotators, but avoid inferring this information. Instead, state that this information is unknown. See Larson, 2017^d for using identity categories as variables, particularly gender.]

Crowd Labour^{e,f}

[Describe the conditions under which the data was annotated (for example, if the annotators were crowdworkers, state what platform was used, or if the data was found, what website the data was found on). If compensation was provided, include that information here.]

Data Provenance^{e,f}

[If applicable, provide additional information on the aspects of provenance that have impacted the data collection, for example ownership, licences and other obligations associated with sources of data, such as rights attached to a physical collection.]

Use of Linked Open Data, Controlled Vocabularies, Multilingual Ontologies/Taxonomies

[Describe linked open data schemes, controlled vocabularies, ontologies and taxonomies if used during the establishment of the dataset. It is appropriate to use a web identifier or link to the vocabulary (possibly version-specific).

NB: this field is aimed to capture the vocabularies that appear as “values” in the data, not the ones used to structure it (which are in scope for the “Compliance with Standards” element in the “Data Structure” section).]

Version Information^f

[Provide information on the dataset version being the subject of this datasheet. Alternatively, provide a release date and a date when the dataset was last updated as well as information on whether there was a previous version of the dataset published before. If relevant, describe which versioning policy drives growing or changing datasets (e.g. systematisation, subsetting for specific purposes). Indicate if the status of previous versions has become deprecated. If the new version differs substantially from the previous one, especially if a dataset grows over time, it is recommended to provide an adapted datasheet.]

Release Date

[If applicable, fill the time stamp of the date of release of this version.]

Date of Modification

[If applicable, fill the time stamp of the date of (minor) modification of this version.]

Checksums

[Provide checksums over here (with a clear mention of the algorithm, e.g. MD5 and SHA256).]

Maintenance plan^{b,f}

[Dataset creators are encouraged to plan for dataset maintenance and communicate this plan to dataset consumers.]

Maintenance level^{b,f}

[Please describe the level of commitment for the maintenance of the dataset. Three suggestions can be used to communicate this: a) *Actively Maintained* – This dataset will be actively maintained, including but not limited to updates to the data. b) *Limited Maintenance* – The data will not be updated, but any technical issues will be addressed c) *No maintenance*.]

Update Periodicity

[If applicable, how frequently is the dataset foreseen to be updated?]

Examples and Considerations for Using the Data^{b,f}

[Dataset creators are encouraged to reflect on the tasks for which the dataset should and should not be used. This section can also provide guidelines on usage.]

Ethical Considerations

Personal and Other Sensitive Information^{c,e,f}

[Sensitive data are better not expressed through quantitative information, but are recommended to be explained narratively. Descriptions might answer the following questions: Who or what are depicted in the dataset? If the dataset depicts people, are any specific subgroups of people represented? Are any specific individuals personally identifiable? If the dataset depicts people, are any individuals still living? Does this project comply with GDPR and privacy laws in the countries where it will be shared? Does this dataset pertain to a difficult history? If so, what extra precautions are being taken? Describe other people represented or mentioned in the data. Where possible, link to references for the information given.

State whether the dataset uses identity categories and, if so, how the information is used. Describe where this information comes from (i.e. self-reporting, collecting from profiles, inferring, etc.). See Larson, 2017^d for using identity categories as variables, particularly gender. State whether the data is linked to individuals and whether those individuals can likely be identified in the dataset, either directly or indirectly (i.e., in combination with other data). State whether the dataset contains other data that might be considered sensitive (e.g., data that reveals racial or ethnic origins, sexual orientations, religious beliefs, political opinions or union memberships, or locations; financial or health data; biometric or genetic data; forms of government identification, such as social security numbers; criminal history). If efforts were made to anonymise the data, describe the anonymisation process. Parts of

this information provided here might be placed instead in the section about biases below.]

Discussion of Biases^c

[Provide descriptions of specific biases that are likely to be reflected in the data, and state whether any steps were taken to reduce their impact. See Blodgett et al., 2020^a for a general discussion of the topic in NLP. If analyses have been run quantifying these biases, please add brief summaries and links to the studies here.]

Potential Societal Impact of Using the Dataset^c

[Discuss some of the ways you believe the use of this dataset could impact society. The statement should include positive outlooks, such as outlining how technologies developed through its use may facilitate new knowledge creation (e.g., if it contains useful data for a low-resource or under-represented language). It should also discuss risks. These risks may range from making important decisions more opaque to people who are affected by the technology, to reinforcing existing harmful biases (whose specifics should be discussed in the previous section), among other considerations. Indicate whether impacted communities have been consulted in the process of curating and publishing the dataset and/or should be involved at reuse stage.]

Examples of Datasets, Publications and Models that (re-)use the Dataset

[Reuse is defined as use of the data regardless of when it is used, the purpose, the characteristics of the data and its user (van de Sandt et al., 2019⁹). If you know that the dataset has been *directly* used to create and publish other datasets, if a researcher uses this data for a particular purpose (e.g., assessing its quality) or if there is a model which has been trained on this dataset, add URL here. “Publications” includes, for instance, other datasheets and (Jupyter) notebooks.]

Known Non-Ethical Limitations^c

[If studies of the datasets have outlined other limitations of the dataset, such as annotation artefacts, please outline and cite them here.]

Unanticipated Uses made of this Dataset^f

[Datasets may be used in contexts that they were not conceived for. As this can open positive opportunities that were not thought of, or cause issues which are specific to a dataset, it is recommended to indicate here the unintended uses that one wants to inform re-users about.]

Bibliography Used for Establishing this Template

^aBlodgett, S. L., Barocas, S., Daumé III, H., & Wallach, H. (2020). Language (Technology) is Power: A Critical Survey of “Bias” in NLP. *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 5454–5476. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.485>

^bGebru, T., Morgenstern, J., Vecchione, B., Vaughan, J. W., Wallach, H., Daumé III, H., & Crawford, K. (2021). Datasheets for Datasets. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(12), 86–92. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3458723>

^cHugging Face Dataset Card Creation Guide, https://github.com/huggingface/datasets/blob/main/templates/README_guide.md

^dLarson, B. N. (2017). Gender as a Variable in Natural-Language Processing: Ethical Considerations. *EthNLP@EACL*. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1%2FW17-1601>

^eLee, B. C. G. (2023). The ‘Collections as ML Data’ Checklist for Machine Learning & Cultural Heritage. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24765>

^fPushkarna, M., Zaldivar, A., & Kjartansson, O. (2022). Data Cards: Purposeful and Transparent Dataset Documentation for Responsible AI. *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 1776–1826. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533231>

^gvan de Sandt, S., Dallmeier-Tiessen, S., Lavasa, A. & Petras, V. (2019). The Definition of Reuse. *Data Science Journal*, 18(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-022>